

Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt and Nickel with *N,N'*-Diphenyldithiomalonamide and Elucidation of Structures of the Compounds

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Cobalt and nickel were extracted into chloroform as *N,N'*-diphenyldithiomalonamide complexes from solutions having pH 6.5–7.0 and 7.0–8.0, and the absorbance values of the extracts were measured at 435 and 420 nm, respectively. These metals were determined with relative standard deviation of 0.18% for Co and 0.12% for Ni. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 0.4–17.0 μg for Co and 0.7–20.0 μg for Ni per ml of the final chloroform solution. The molar absorptivities and Sandell sensitivities were $3.27 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1.80 \times 10^{-3} \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for Co and 1.48×10^4 and 3.95×10^{-3} for Ni. The interferences of various ions were studied, and conditions were developed for the determinations of the metals in certain alloys and synthetic mixtures.

Ir and nmr spectroscopic studies were used in order to establish the type of coordination between *N,N'*-diphenyldithiomalonamide and the metal ions. It is concluded from the nmr spectra that the nickel complex exists in two isomeric forms in the ratio of 8 : 2 and the cobalt complex has only one modification.

In the present investigation *N,N'*-diphenyldithiomalonamide¹ [(C₆H₅NH.CS)₂CH₂], DPDTM (1), a new reagent coordinating through two thiocarbonyl groups instead of two carbonyl groups or one thiocarbonyl and one carbonyl group as in β -diketones and monothio derivative of the same, has been introduced for the first time in the conventional β -ketones structure with the expectation of being selective for soft and borderline metal ions. The xanthates and substituted-xanthates are widely used for sensitive and selective complexing agents for the polarisable metal ions²⁻⁹. Similarly, the derivatives of thiocarbazones are used widely as analytical reagents¹⁰⁻¹². During the studies on thio derivatives of β -ketoanilides, it is found¹ that DPDTM (1) offers interesting analytical possibilities, superior to that of acetothioacetanilide^{14,15} and the corresponding substituted- β -diketones^{16,17} owing to the higher molar absorptivities of the chelates. Though *in situ* preparations of dithio-metal complexes have been reported^{18,19}, the analytical properties of the reagents have not been studied.

In this paper, which forms a part of a systematic investigation of the analytical applications of *N,N'*-diphenyldithiomalonamide, a detailed study of the experimental conditions involved in the formation of Co(DPDTM)₂ and Ni(DPDTM)₂ complexes are reported. The stable and very symmetrical reagent has been applied to the simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of cobalt and nickel in mixtures as well as in some alloys.

Experimental

Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out using a Varian Cary-17D spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cells. The pH measurements were carried out with a EC 5652 digital pH meter.

N,N'-Diphenyldithiomalonamide was prepared according to the reported method²⁰. Sodium (0.01 mol) dissolved in dry absolute ethanol (30 ml) was added to acetylacetone (0.01 mol) with stirring at room temperature. After 5 min, phenylisothiocyanate (0.02 mol) was added to it. The solution was kept cold for 24 h, then poured into ice-cold water to give a lemon-yellow solid sparingly soluble in alcohol, m.p. 152° (Found: C, 62.4; H, 4.8; N, 9.7; S, 22.4. C₁₆H₁₄N₂S₂ requires: C, 62.9; H, 4.9; N, 9.8; S 22.4%). A 0.05% chloroform solution of the reagent was used for the determinations. Standard solutions (0.05%) of cobalt(II) (9.65 mg ml⁻¹) and nickel(II) (14.64 mg ml⁻¹) were prepared from cobalt nitrate hexahydrate and nickel sulphate hexahydrate, respectively and the solutions were standardised by conventional methods^{21,22}. Working standard solutions were prepared by suitable dilution of the standard solution.

All the chemicals used were of A.R. or G.R. grade.

General procedure: Each sample solution (~20 ml) containing 4–9 μg of Co or 3–12 μg of Ni was transferred into a 100 ml separatory funnel with a tightly fitting stopper. The solution was then

heated to $\sim 70^\circ$ on a water-bath followed by addition of 0.05% ethanolic DPDTM solution (0.5 ml). pH was adjusted to 6.5–7.0 for Co and 7.0–8.0 for Ni using ammonia solution (1 M). The solution was allowed to stand for 3 min and the complex formed extracted with chloroform (2 \times 4 ml). The extracts were mixed together, dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and transferred to a 10 ml measuring flask to make up the volume with chloroform. The absorbances were measured at 435 nm for Co and 420 nm for Ni against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Spectral characteristics : The absorption spectra of DPDTM and its cobalt and nickel complexes in chloroform were recorded against chloroform and the reagent blank, respectively. The maximum absorptions were found to be 337 nm for the reagent, 435 nm for the cobalt complexes and 420 nm for the nickel complexes. The absorption of the reagent was negligible at 470 nm onwards. Other common organic solvents could also be used for the extraction of the complexes from water. However, chloroform was preferred as the absorbance of each metal complex was found to be maximal in this solvent. The molar absorptivities and Sandell sensitivities were $3.27 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1.80 \times 10^{-5} \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for Co and 1.48×10^4 and 3.95×10^{-5} for Ni, respectively. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 0.4–17.0 μg for Co and 0.7–20.0 μg for Ni per ml of the final chloroform solution.

Effect of pH, reagent concentration, stability of colour and effect of number of extraction : The effect of pH of the extraction was studied by extracting the same quantity of the metal concerned with 60% excess reagent at different pH values and measuring the absorbances of extracts. The absorbance of the cobalt(III) was found to reach a constant value over the pH range 6.5–7.0. The subsequent determinations were carried out at pH 6.8. For nickel(II), the pH range for quantitative extraction was 7.0–8.0. In the case of nickel, the determinations were carried out at pH 7.5. The absorbances of the complexes were studied as a function of varying amounts of reagent concentrations keeping the same quantity of metal concerned at the pH values cited above. It was observed that approximately 60% excess reagent was needed to obtain the maximum absorbance, which afterwards remained constant with the increase in concentration. The absorbances of both the complexes remained unchanged for more than ten weeks after extraction. The recovery of the complexes to the extent of about 95% in the first step was observed.

Nature of complexes : The molar composition of both the complexes formed under the conditions described for the determinations of cobalt and nickel were ascertained by Job's method of continuous variations and mole-ratio method. Both the methods indicated the formation of a 1:3 (metal–ligand) cobalt and 1:2 nickel complexes.

The ready oxidation of cobalt(II) to cobalt(III) has also been reported for the complexes with some soft bases^{23,24} like nitrate, cyanide and monothio β -diketones²⁵. The stoichiometries were further confirmed in the preceding section from the analytical results.

The DPDTM complexes of cobalt and nickel were isolated and dried under reduced pressure. The ir spectra (KBr) of the chelates and the reagent DPDTM have been studied in the solid phase. It was observed that the metal sulphur stretching frequency expected in the range 360–380 cm^{-1} was not observed in either cases. The $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ is not always observed as described by Martin *et al.*^{26,27}.

The ^1H nmr spectra of the ligand was obtained from a solution of DPDTM in a mixture of CDCl_3 and DMSO-d_6 . The spectra of the nickel(II) and cobalt(III) complexes were obtained from CDCl_3 solution. The data are given in Table 1. The spectra of DPDTM show the presence of two methylene signals at δ 4.4 and 4.3 in the ratio of about 9 : 1. This suggests that in solution there is a mixture of conformers 1 and 2. The small broad signal at 11.24 ppm indicates the presence of the hydrogen bonded proton as in the structure 2.

TABLE 1—NMR SIGNALS FOR DPDTM AND ITS NiII AND CoIII COMPLEXES

Compd.	Chemical shift	Assignment	Structure
DPDTM	4.4(s), 4.3(s) 7.2–7.87(m) 10.16 (br. peak) 11.24 (br. signal)	OH_2 ArH NH–Ph NH–Ph (hydrogen bonded)	1, 2
Ni(DPDTM) ₂	4.10(s) 5.95(s) 6.75–7.59(m) 11.0(s)	OH_2 O=OH ArH NH–Ph (hydrogen bonded)	3, 4
Co(DPDTM) ₃	6.10(s) 7.10–7.25(m) 7.70(s)	O=OH ArH NH–Ph	

The spectra of the nickel complex indicate the presence of two forms 3 and 4 in a ratio of about 4 : 1.

The spectra of the cobalt complex indicates the presence of only one isomer which is considered to have structure 5. The singlet at δ 7.7 is tentatively assigned to the PhN-H protons. Such an abnormal upfield shift of the PhN-H proton is probably due to the forced placement of the proton in the shielding zone of the π -cloud due to steric ground.

The analysis report for the complexes are as follows : the Co complex, Found : Co, 6.4 ; C, 59.0 ; H, 4.3 ; N, 9.1 ; S, 20.6. Calcd. Co, 6.4 ; C, 59.1 ; H, 4.3 ; N, 9.2 ; S, 21.0% ; the Ni complex follows : Found : Ni, 9.3 ; C, 56.4 ; H, 4.2 ; N, 8.5 ; S, 19.9. Calcd. Ni, 9.3 ; C, 57.3 ; H, 4.1 ; N, 8.9 ; S, 20.4%. The magnetic behaviour of the complexes indicates the square-planar low-spin arrangement for the nickel complex and octahedral low-spin arrangement for the cobalt complex. In the latter case, the transitions of electron from $^1A_{1g}$ ground state takes place to $^1T_{1g}$ and $^1T_{2g}$ excited states. The molecular ion (M^+) peak could not be obtained for any one of the chelates owing to pyrolysis of the complexes.

The effect of 32 cations and 7 anions on the determination of cobalt and nickel was tested by the proposed method. The tolerance limits for interferants are as reported earlier²⁸. Tolerance values (μ g) of interfering ions on the determination of 7.72 μ g of Co^{II} and 10.98 μ g Ni^{II} are as follows : alkali and alkaline earth metals, Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} (in presence of fluoride), Mn^{II} , fluoride, chloride, bromide, sulphate and nitrate (150) ; Cr^{III} , V^{VI} , W^{VI} , Zn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Bi^{III} (worked with turbid solution) ; As^V , Sb^{III} , citrate, tartrate and cyanide (100) ; Mo^{VI} , Cd^{II} and Sn^{II} (10) ; Cu^{II} (5). The tolerance limits show that both nickel and cobalt can be determined in the presence of large number of ions. High concentrations (>150-fold excess) of Fe^{II} or Fe^{III} can be masked by fluoride ion. Na_2 -EDTA, and sulphide interfered in the determinations. These ions do not affect the determination of nickel and cobalt when present in at least 10-fold excess of Mo^{VI} , Cd^{II} , Cu^{II} and Sn^{II} . So the determinations of nickel and cobalt were possible in alloy samples. Cobalt was separated from nickel by selective precipitation²⁹ by controlling the pH at 6.5–6.8. The precipitated cobalt complex was filtered and dissolved in chloroform to determine the cobalt concentration at 435 nm. Then the concentration of nickel was determined after the removal of cobalt as described under procedure.

Determination of Co and Ni in alloys : Each sample (0.1–1.0 g) of the alloys of nickel and cobalt was dissolved in concentrated HCl (15–20 ml), followed by concentrated HNO_3 (few drops) with heating. The solution was then evaporated to dryness, another portion of concentrated HCl (10 ml) was added, diluted with water, filtered and the filtrate diluted to 500 ml in a calibrated flask. For the determination of nickel or cobalt, an aliquot of the sample solution was taken and diluted to 15 ml. Sodium fluoride (~0.1 g) dissolved in water (5 ml) was then added to mask iron, if present in large amount (>10-fold excess). The aqueous phase was then treated as described under the procedure for the successful determination of nickel or cobalt in steel, high speed steel, stainless steel and aluminium–nickel alloy samples.

References

1. T. PAL, A. GANGULY and D. S. MAITY, Presented at International Symposium on Metals Speciation, Separation and Recovery, Chicago, 1986.
2. A. K. DE, *Sep Sci*, 1968, 3, 103.
3. E. M. DONALDSON, *Talanta*, 1982, 29, 663.
4. A. L. J. RAO and S. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 503.
5. A. L. J. RAO and S. SINGH, *Fresenius Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1971, 257, 139.
6. M. F. HUSSAIN and B. K. BANSAL, *Croat. Chem. Acta*, 1984, 57, 219.
7. M. F. HUSSAIN, R. K. BANSAL, B. K. PURI and M. SATAKE, *Analyst*, 1984, 109, 1151.
8. M. F. HUSSAIN, R. K. BANSAL, B. K. PURI and M. SATAKE, *Analyst*, 1984, 109, 1291.
9. M. F. HUSSAIN, R. K. BANSAL, B. K. PURI and M. SATAKE, *Analyst*, 1985, 110, 1131.
10. R. B. SINGH, D. S. GARG and R. P. SINGH, *Talanta*, 1978, 25, 619.
11. J. M. C. PAVON, *Microchem. J.*, 1981, 26, 155.
12. J. M. C. PAVON, D. PEREZ BENDITO and M. VALCARCEL, *Quim. Anal.*, 1982, 118.
13. J. M. C. PAVON, A. G. DE TORRES and B. OJEDA, *Analyst*, 1985, 110, 1137.
14. K. DE (DATTA) and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1026.
15. T. PAL and J. DAS, *Talanta*, 1983, 30, 519.
16. M. DAS and S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1974, 27, 59.
17. S. E. LIVINGSTONE and J. E. OLUKA, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1976, 29, 1913.
18. L. XIANTE, H. JINLING and H. JIANQUAR, *Zwan Zashu*, 1982, 5, 949 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1984, 99, 15410).
19. K. KNAUER, P. HEMMERICH and J. D. W. VANTVOORST, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Eng.*, 1967, 6, 262.
20. V. G. BARNIKOW, V. KATH and D. RICHTER, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1965, 30, 63.
21. H. HERVELD and O. GERNGROSS, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1984, 98, 408.
22. O. BRUNKE, *Angew. Chem.*, 1914, 27, 315.
23. R. G. FRARSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 3533.
24. S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Quart. Rev.*, 1965, 19, 386.
25. S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, 7, 67.
26. A. R. HENDRICKSON and R. L. MARTIN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, 12, 2582.
27. T. N. LOCKYER and R. L. MARTIN, *Progr. Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, 27, 223.
28. T. PAL and D. S. MAITY, *Analyst*, 1986, 111, 49.
29. T. PAL, A. GANGULY, D. S. MAITY and S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Talanta*, 1986, 33, 973.